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Impact of the Divine Word College of Vigan MBA Program in Region 1 and Cordillera Autonomous Region (CAR), Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Job security and high salary are some of the most important reasons why MBA programs are so popular nowadays. This study identified the impact of the Divine Word College of Vigan's MBA program in Region 1 and Cordillera Autonomous Region (CAR) Philippines for the School Year 2021-2022. Factors included the assessment of the respondent's age, sex, civil status, nature of employment, and residence. Graduates' assessment of the level of performance of the DWCV graduate program was expressed in terms of program relevance, faculty qualification, research facilities, classrooms, laboratory, library facilities, and achievable goals. The level of impact of training in the MBA program was measured using four (4) indicators: training and productivity, training on professional development and advancement, training on professional recognition, life-long skills (socio-economic development). A descriptive survey with a correlational method was employed in the study. A questionnaire was utilized extensively to survey the impact of the Divine Word College of Vigan MBA Program on Region 1 and CAR students. Respondents of the study were the 68 graduates of the MBA program in the school years 2018-2019; 2019-2020; and 2020-2021. The socio-demographic profile of the respondents was statistically treated with the use of frequency count and percentage. Weighted mean and t-tests were used to determine the level of assessment on the performance of the MBA program, the impact of its training, and their correlations respectively. between the respondent's profile, the MBA program's performance, and its training program's impact, respectively. t-test was used for the correlation of the relationship between the profile of respondents and the assessment of the performance of the MBA program and its impact on training in the MBA program.

Based on the problems raised in this study, the hypotheses show that there is a significant relationship between age and the assessment of MBA programs in terms of program relevance, faculty qualification, research facilities, and the achieved goals of MBA programs. On the other hand, the table shows that program relevance has also a significant relationship with sex. Further, a significant relationship was identified between training on productivity. The training on professional development and professional recognition are significantly related to sex. The impact of training in an MBA program is significantly related to the assessment of the respondents in the MBA program of DWCV except on the life-long skills and achieved goals of the MBA program.

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Introduction

The MBA program in the Philippines, according to EDCOM Report (2016), has been generally successful as it has supplied the managerial force among many private organizations as well as public offices. Many of those who

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graduated from the country's best MBA schools are the leaders in the government and industry today, deciding how companies are seen, shaping the destinies of industries, and charting the course of the nation.

The claims of Encio et. al. (2018) support the idea that graduate studies are a lifelong learning commitment that brings more opportunities for personal growth and professional development. Specifically, the MBA program gives graduates a better opportunity to get new jobs, attain a regular permanent status, and be considered for the job. The study by Menez (2014) showed that 100 percent of the surveyed university's MBA graduates from 2013 to 2015 were locally employed and garnered a higher result employment rating of 96% from 2008-2012. Notably, an MBA degree is one of the requirements for promotion in most companies. Likewise, findings of the study of Hay and Hodgkinson (2006) revealed a diversity of meanings given to MBA career success, with the success generally being expressed in much broader terms than conventional notions of fast-track career advancement.

Arcelo (2010) opined that higher education must go beyond the academic realm. It must focus on providing the skills, knowledge, and values that enable graduates to contribute meaningfully to accelerate economic political, spiritual, and social development. For instance, the Asian Institute of Management (AIM) based in Makati City, Philippines has been the training ground for Asia's managers. Indeed, a consistent edge for the Philippines has been its management and business education quality. The hard and soft skills learned during an MBA program can open numerous opportunities across different industries (www.cnn.ph).

However, MBA education has also weaknesses (Arcelo, 2010). Yip's (2017) study divulged some of these as follows: low quality of faculty, lack of research skills, low retention rate in the program, limited research skills, and the absence of actual industry experience. Underscoring the retention rate, EDCOM Report (2016), correctly cited the motivation to pursue graduate studies as hampered by the conduct of research over the financial rewards of finishing the program.

The findings of the study therefore would be helpful to the researcher in assessing the strengths and weaknesses of the MBA program that may lead to further improvement. It would also be an insightful assessment of DWCV's MBA program's delivery of the quality program to the stakeholders.

The study is divided into five parts. The first part is the introduction, which discusses the study's rationale and objective. The second part is the review of the related literature and studies related to the concept of impact theory, change theory, human capital theory, concept on impact, the past and present MBA programs, and the conceptual framework of the study. The third part is the research methodology which discusses the research design, population, research instruments, data gathering procedures, the locale of the study, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is the empirical data and analysis. The final part is about the discussion of results, implications, and conclusion of the study.

Literature Review

To have a greater insight into the concepts of impact study in business education, ideas from authorities and experts were incorporated in this section as a basis of understanding.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Impact Theory, Change Theory, and Human Capital Theory

According to Tom Bilyeu (2013), impact theory is designed to give people the tools and knowledge they need to unlock their potential and impact the world. The theory explores the mindsets of the world's highest achievers to learn their secrets to success (impacttheory.com). Change theory involves a theory for planning, participation, and evaluation that is used in companies' philanthropy, not-for-profit, and government sectors to promote social change. It also defines long-term goals and then maps backward to identify necessary preconditions. It is also a description of why a particular way of working will be effective, showing how change happens in the short, medium, and long term to achieve the indebted impact (knowledge.ncvo.org). The human capital theory describes the benefits of having an advanced degree as part of investment in preparation for whatever higher responsibility in the future. This study uses insights from human capital theory to explain how education helps employees to improve their job posts and performance based on the learning outcomes of them their completed master's degree program in Business Administration. In human capital theory as cited in Benson et.al. (2004), skills are viewed as enablers of productivity that firms compensate individuals for through wages. Olaniyan and Okemakinde (2008), noted that the focus on education as capital goods relates to the concept of human capital, which emphasizes that the development of skills is an important factor in production activities. Meanwhile, Ng and Feldman (2009), emphasized that educated employees, as a group, perform more effectively at a task, citizenship, and counterproductive performance, and that certainly predicts well for the fulfillment of managers' expectations of highly educated workers.

Concept on Impact

Fahy, Spencer, and Halinski (2009) found out that the major impacts of graduate program completion were on personal confidence, credibility as seen by others, and promotion potential. Menez (2014) stated that earning a master's degree is a self-fulfillment based on interviews with some of the MBS graduates from her previous study. However, Knowles and Hensher (2005) noted that there is little doubt that the traditional business program fails to produce students with many of the soft skills demanded by employers. The study of Camuffo, Gerli, Borgo, and Somia (2009) revealed that the degree of competency development during the MBA program enhances career advancement such as planning, result orientation, networking, organizational awareness, system thinking, and the use of technology. Likewise, Baruch and Peiperl (2000) found out that the MBA degree does have an impact.

The MBA Program, Past, and Present

Aleamory (2008) mentioned that in the history of professional education, training is a relative newcomer. Up to the end of the 19th century, business training for the most part meant apprenticeship, either in the family firm or as trainees in one of the larger training houses or merchant banks. By the end of the century, business schools had been established at the University of California at Berkeley. Four more were established in 1900 and by 1925 there were 183. Knowles (2005) expressed that the University of Chicago was the first to offer a graduate business program, but it was the Harvard Graduate School of Business, established in 1908, which pioneered the development of the MBA program. Upham (2010) informed that from humble beginnings, at the turn of the century, MBA programs have grown

immensely. While there are variations, most MBA programs have a similar core curriculum that encompasses five broad areas: foundation subjects, functional subjects, behavioral subjects, environmental subjects, and integrative subjects. Included among the foundation subjects are economics, statistics, mathematics, and more recently, data processing.

Government Concerns for Research and Socio-Economic Factors

On September 5, 1974, at the time of the “Bureau of Private Schools, Department of Education and Culture”, circular no. 10, s. 1974 was issued to “Heads of Private Schools, Colleges and Universities” continuing the “Rules and Standards for Graduate Education”. This was signed by BPS Director B. Yballe, with the approval of Juan L. Manuel to take effect in the school year 1975-1976. The first two provisions of the circular state were the role of graduate education in national development and the venue of individual and institutional research for innovations. Unfortunately.

Arcelo (2010) divulged a wide perception that the MBA program has limited supervision. According to Todaro (2010), the rapid quantitative expansion of educational opportunities is the key to national development. Naval (2017), likewise, mentioned that graduate education serves as the focal point of creating the next generation of advances in society, government, business, and education. Ramirez (2017) opined that research on sustainable development fosters the security of future generations.

Haggins (2001) discussed research along with empirical evidence which takes four main forms: (1) growth accounting studies which estimate the contribution to economic growth in a given period of investment in the education of labor forces; (2) productivity studies, which points out the contribution of additional education to the physical productivity of workers; (3) cost-benefit studies which evaluate the economic contribution of education and training in terms of their private costs, earnings foregone, and (4) other expenses incurred by students while in school, public costs, and additional income earned by those who benefit from the education in poverty alleviation.

Wang (2002) strongly believed that research capability should be instilled among graduate professionals. A good quality indicator is when graduate students are researchers that can establish a reputation for themselves within any given discipline.

Specifically, Cepe’s (2018) study assessed the status of the graduate programs of Region IV which ascertained their extent in responding to the desired standards and excellence in graduate education using ten variables including research and other scholarly activities. One of the findings highlighted the limited funds for research as perceived by the faculty. Meanwhile, the students assessed that research was taught as a course, and they are required to conduct research for publication in journals.

Concept on Quality

Woodhouse (2010) says that many governments are committing a large percentage of public funds to higher education. Considering the increasing funds allocated to education, the government needs to be reassured on three counts: HEIs’ aim to produce graduates required by society; the money spent well on efficient operations; HEIs’ effective operation

of producing the desired graduates. Woodhouse (2010) further came out with the quality theory in response to the increasing importance of issues of quality assurance in the higher education sector.

These concerns lead to a great increase in the activities external to the HEIs which might be called external quality review and the establishment of quality assurance. This refers to the policies, attributes, actions, and procedures necessary to ensure that quality is maintained and enhanced. It may include any or more of the following approaches: quality audit, quality assessment, quality accreditation, and quality improvement.

Concept of Knowledge Development and Technology Transfer

Indolos (2008) cited that Schumacher views education as the “greatest resource”. No economy can do without an educated class and skilled manpower. Indeed, there is a persuasive body of evidence that investment in the education and training of the labor force plays a crucial role in economic development. According to McNulty (2005), while management may never become a profession in the traditional sense, the actions of countless individuals continue to professionalize its critical work.

Upham (2010) further emphasized that when the stakes are high, the frontier of graduate education is what makes the university the most revolutionary modern institution of learning in the world. For instance, Quevada (2017) shared that while the Philippines is making strides toward strengthening its intellectual property laws, local major universities face several hurdles when it comes to technology transfer.

Faculty Qualification

De la Cruz (2014) assessed the status of the MBA program, in Region I as a basis for building a development framework. His findings on the competencies of the faculty showed that while the majority of the deans are doctoral degree holders, they are mostly in the field of education (e.g. Ed. D.), instead of business.

The majority of the MBA schools (six of them) have less than 60 percent degree holders, and the teaching strategies used are still largely traditional. For instance, Aleamory (2008) cited that student evaluation of faculty performance is the most widely used technique to measure qualification and competence inside the classroom here and abroad. He offers the following arguments to support the use of student rating: students are the main source of information about the learning environment, including the teacher’s ability to motivate students for continued learning, and rapport between the instructor and students; they are more logical in evaluating the effectiveness of teacher and their satisfaction with the course content, method of instruction, textbooks, homework, and seatwork, and ratings given by students foster a smooth relationship with their instructors.

Library Facilities

The study of de la Cruz (2014) revealed that in many of the schools, library holdings and reference materials are inadequate and outdated, while access to internet facilities is limited. Similarly, the study of Dilanco (2007) on the MBA programs of the University of Nueva Caceres and Ateneo de Naga revealed some challenges perceived by both the faculty and the students, namely facilities, curriculum, and research requirements.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Figure 1: The conceptual framework reflects the relationship between the profile and performance of the MBA program; the profile and the impact of training, and the performance of the MBA program and its impact on training.

Statement of the Problems

This study determined the impact of the Divine Word College of Vigan, MBA program in Region 1, and Cordillera Autonomous Region (CAR). More specifically, this study answered the following:

1. **What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:**
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 civil status;
 - 1.4 nature of employment, and
 - 1.5 residence?
2. **What is the level of performance of the DWCV MBA program along:**
 - 2.1 program relevance;
 - 2.2 faculty qualification;
 - 2.3 research facilities;
 - 2.4 classrooms and laboratory facilities;
 - 2.5 library facilities, and
 - 2.5 achievable goals?
3. **What is the level of impact of training in the MBA program in terms of:**
 - 3.1 training and productivity;
 - 3.2 training on professional development and advancement;
 - 3.3 training on professional recognition, and
 - 3.4 life-long skills (socio-economic development)?

4. *Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their assessment of the performance of the MBA program?*
5. *Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the impact of training in the MBA program?*
6. *Is there a significant relationship between the assessment of the performance of the MBA program and the impact of training in the MBA program?*

Assumptions

The study assumed that the impact of the Divine Word College of Vigan MBA program in Region 1 and (CAR) as perceived by the graduate students can be measured. The instrument used to measure the program's impact is valid and reliable. The responses of the respondents express their true feelings/reactions to each item of the questionnaire.

Hypotheses

Fahy, Spencer, and Halinski (2009) found out that the major impacts of graduate program completion were on personal confidence, credibility as seen by others, and promotion potential. Based on this premise, the study indicated that the profile of DWCV's MBA graduate students, the assessment of its program, and the impact of its training have significant relationships in the delivery of the quality program to the stakeholders.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study was undertaken essentially to determine the impact of the Divine Word College of Vigan MBA program in region 1 and Cordillera Administrative Region (CAR), Philippines, School Year 2021-2022.

Research Methodology

This presents the overall research plan, procedures, and steps undertaken in the research study. It discusses the research method used, sources of data, data gathering instruments, and the statistical tools utilized in treating the data gathered about a topic (Wilkinson, 2000, Leedy, 1974). Furthermore, this study followed the rule of procedures in the investigation by determining the research design, data gathering instruments method, the population of the study, the locale of the study, the data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

This study applied the descriptive survey with the correlational method employed in the study. The descriptive method according to Medel (2009), involves description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the present nature. It defines the nature of one certain phenomenon depending on the levels of description (askinglot.com). This approach is used to describe the performance and impact of training of the Divine Word College of Vigan MBA program in Region 1 and (CAR). On the other hand, the correlation method according to Kalla (2011), is a tool to determine whether two variables are connected.

Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was the Divine Word College of Vigan in Region 1 and Cordillera Administrative Region (CAR), Philippines, School Year 2021-2022.

Population

The respondents of the study were the 79 graduates of the MBA program in the school years 2018-2019; 2019-2020 and 2020-2021. The population of the study was determined by random sampling. Out of 79 graduates, only 68 responded for about 86 percent retrieved rate. Forty-two (42) respondents were from (CAR) while twenty-six (26) respondents were from Region 1.

Data Gathering Instruments

The questionnaire was adapted from the study of Reynaldo Cruz (2016) entitled “Perceived Impact Study of the University of Regina Carmeli (URC) Graduate School in Three Master’s Degree Programs: Teacher Education, Business Education, and Public Administration”. This adaptation ensured its content validity of 4.90 and reliability value of 0.899 Cronbach’s Alpha. The questionnaire consisted of three parts. Part I solicited the data on the five personal factors of respondents. Part II contained questions to identify the performance of DWCV graduate school in terms of program relevance, faculty qualification, research facilities, classroom and laboratory facilities, library facilities, and achievable goals. Part III was composed of questions about the impact of the MBA program which was measured in terms of training and productivity, training on professional development and advancement, training on professional recognition, and life-long skills (social and economic development).

Data Gathering Procedures

In the pursuit of the objectives of the study, the researcher first sought the permission of the president of Divine Word College of Vigan to conduct the study. Then the researcher personally contacted the respondents to get the necessary data from them. Filled-up questionnaires were returned through LBC, email, and personal submission.

Ethical Considerations

To establish and safeguard ethics in conducting this research, the researcher strictly observed the following: the researcher made sure that the content of the questionnaire will not hurt any person or organization which ensured that responses were subjected to research; proper document sourcing or referencing of materials was done to promote copyright laws; a letter of request was presented to the concerned authorities, and the researcher explained the research instrument to the respondents.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The frequency count and percentage were used to categorize the respondents according to their socio-demographic profile of the respondents. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of assessment on the performance of the graduate school and the impact of the training in the MBA program. The t-test was used for the correlation of the

variables: the respondents' profile, the performance of the MBA program, and the impact of training. The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation were used:

Level of Performance of the MBA program:

<i>Legend:</i>	
4.21 – 5.00	Excellent (E)
3.41 – 4.20	Very Good (VG)
2.61 – 3.40	Good (G)
1.81 – 2.60	Fair (F)
1.00 – 1.80	Poor (P)

Level of Impact of Training in the MBA graduate program:

<i>Legend:</i>	
4.21 – 5.00	Very Great Extent (VGE)
3.41 – 4.20	Great Extent (GE)
2.61 – 3.40	Average Extent (AE)
1.81 – 2.60	Little Extent (LE)
1.00 – 1.80	Very Little Extent (VLE)

Data Presentation and Analysis

This part presents data that was gathered through research questionnaires and the presentation follows the statement of the problems. The data are in the table and followed by the analysis.

Problem 1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

- 1.1 age;
- 1.2 sex;
- 1.3 civil status;
- 1.4 nature of employment, and
- 1.5 residence?

Table 1. presents the socio-demographic profile of the MBA students of DWCV.

Socio-demographic Profile	f	%
Age		
20-24	4	5.88
25-29	21	30.88
30-34	9	13.24
35-39	13	19.12
40-44	7	10.29
45-49	7	10.29
50-54	7	10.29
Total	68	100.00
Sex		
Male	25	36.76
Female	43	63.24
Total	68	100.00
Civil Status		
Single	32	47.06
Married	36	52.94
Widow	-	-
Total	68	100.00
Nature of Employment		
Professional/Technical Workers	9	13.24
Administrative/Executive Managerial Workers	2	2.93
Clerical and Related Workers	9	13.24
Sales	-	-
Service	-	-
Production	-	-
Government Employee	48	70.59
Total	68	100.00
Place of Residence		
Cordillera Administrative Region	42	61.76
Region I	26	38.24
Total	68	100.00

The table shows that 30.88% are in the bracket of 25-29 years old. In terms of sex, the table reveals that most of the respondents are female (43 or 63.24%). Most of the respondents are married 52.94%. The table further shows that the nature of employment of the respondents is categorized mostly as government employees (70.59%). The table revealed further that most of the respondents (61.76%) are from the (Cordillera Administrative Region).

2. What is the level of performance of the DWCV Graduate Program along:

- 2.1 program relevance;
- 2.2 faculty qualification;
- 2.3 research facilities;
- 2.4 classroom and laboratory facilities;
- 2.5 library facilities, and
- 2.6 achieved goals?

Table 2.1 presents the level of performance of the DWCV graduate program on program relevance.

Items	\bar{x}	DR
The program of studies is consistent with the national goal, and the specific objectives of the graduate school.	4.81	E
The program of studies responds to the needs for professional and technical preparation of graduate students.	4.78	E
The curriculum keeps abreast with contemporary issues and concerns.	4.68	E
The curriculum provides depth and breadth in both foundation and professional courses.	4.66	E
The program studies have adequate provisions for the development of research skills.	4.53	E
Weighted Average	4.69	E

It can be seen in the table that the weighted average of the performance of the graduate school on program relevance by the respondents is an “excellent” assessment with a weighted average of 4.69. All indicators in the performance of program’s relevance were consistently rated in the “excellent” assessment. Excellence reflects DWCV’s MBA program as it supports education as the greatest resource as stated by Indolos (2008)) who cited Schumacher emphasizing that no economy can do without an educated class and skilled manpower.

Table 2.2 presents the level of performance of the graduate program on faculty qualification by the MBA graduate students.

Items	\bar{x}	DR
The faculty members are holders of appropriate doctorate/master’s degrees.	4.54	E
The faculty members show mastery of the subject matter.	4.58	E
The faculty members manifest awareness of current issues, trends, and problems.	4.58	E
The faculty members demonstrate mastery of research skills.	4.58	E
Weighted Average	4.57	E

It could be gleaned from table 2.2 that the respondents rated the graduate school performance on faculty qualification as “excellent” with a mean rating of 4.57. The indicators when taken singly are also rated excellent. Aleamory (2008) cited that student evaluation of faculty performance is the most widely used technique to measure qualification and competence inside the classroom.

The assessment of the level performance of the graduate program in terms of research facilities is reflected in Table 2.3

Items	\bar{x}	DR
Research is an integral part of all course requirements.	4.59	E
The administration provides a functional research and statistical center.	4.29	E
Sufficient statistical assistance for research is provided by qualified faculty members.	4.47	E
There is a reasonable equivalency between research and teaching.	4.59	E
There is evidence that the research outputs of the Graduate School are by acceptable standards.	4.56	E
Weighted Average	4.50	E

The development of research culture is influenced by the quality of research facilities support given by the institution. In this view, the respondents were asked to assess this provision. Table 2c shows that the respondents made “excellent” assessments of the provision as evidenced in the weighted average of 4.50. All indicators are rated the same. Wang (2002) strongly believed that research capability should be instilled among graduate professionals since this is a good quality indicator of a good reputation in any given discipline.

The assessment of the level of performance of the graduate program in terms of classroom and laboratory facilities is revealed in Table 2.4

Items	\bar{x}	DR
There are enough classrooms conducive to teaching and learning processes.	4.31	E
The Graduate School has the necessary laboratory facilities.	4.01	VG
The Graduate School has a consultation room and other function rooms which provide privacy.	4.21	E
It has the necessary equipment to support the instructional and research needs of graduate students.	4.24	E
There is a functional computer center that provides for the computer needs of students and researchers.	4.04	VG
Weighted Average	4.16	VG

It is revealed in the table that the assessment of the classroom and laboratory facilities is at the “very good” level as evidenced by the overall weighted mean rating of 4.16. Most of the indicators were rated “excellent” and “very good” Woodhouse’s (2010) study on quality theory responded to the increasing importance of issues of quality assurance in the higher education sector.”.

Table 2.5 presents the assessments on the level of the performance of the graduate program on the library facilities of the graduate school.

Items	\bar{x}	DR
There are professional librarians to meet the needs of the graduate students and faculty.	4.00	VG
The collection of books, periodicals, and other library materials is adequate to support the demands of scholarship in instruction and research.	4.04	VG
There is a strong reference collection for literature searches, background readings, and information sources.	4.09	VG
The library has an atmosphere conducive to readings and study.	4.07	VG
The library is well-lighted and properly ventilated.	4.12	VG
Weighted Average	4.06	VG

The assessment of the classroom and laboratory facilities is at the “very good” level as evidenced by the overall weighted average of 4.06. Most of the indicators were rated “excellent” and “very good”.

Table 2.6 presents the assessments on the level of the performance of the graduate program on the achieved goals of their graduate students.

Items	\bar{x}	DR
Provide for a graduate education that is Catholic and Divinian in character and responsive to local and international standards of quality and excellence.	4.66	E
Promote the development of critical thinking among students in the analysis of issues and concerns.	4.71	E
Train students to become an agent of change in organizations through knowledge development and technology transfer.	4.66	E
Develop leaders grounded with sound management principles and theories and with sufficient exposure to contemporary issues and problems.	4.66	E
Create a nationalist perspective in responding to issues and problems.	4.66	E
Weighted Average	4.67	E

The respondents in the MBA program of Divine Word College of Vigan perceived that their achieved goals had been addressed by their training to an “excellent” assessment in varying points rated at 4.67. The weighted average of 4.67 indicates that the goals of the graduate school have been achieved to “excellent” assessment.

3. What is the Level of Impact of Training in the MBA Program in terms of:

- 3.1 training on productivity;*
- 3.2 training on professional development and advancement;*
- 3.3 training on professional recognition; and*
- 3.4 life-long skills (socio-economic development)?*

Table 3.1 presents respondents’ perceptions of the level of impact of training in the MBA program in terms of productivity.

Items	\bar{x}	DR
Increased job knowledge.	4.65	VGE
Improved research skills.	4.74	VGE
Improved communication skills.	4.72	VGE
Improved self-confidence.	4.71	VGE
Weighted Average	4.70	VGE

The perception of the MBA graduates on the impact of their graduate training on productivity has a “very great extent” of impact as rated at 4.70. In terms of improved research skills ($x=4.74$), improved communications skills ($x=4.72$), improved self-confidence ($x=4.71$), and increased job knowledge ($x=4.65$). The same trend of impact was reported by MBA graduates. It may be gleaned that the training provided by the graduate school contributed to a “very great extent) with a weighted rating of (4.70). The studies of Camuffo, Gerli, Borgo, and Somia (2009) revealed that the MBA program’s competency development enhances career advancement such as planning, result orientation, networking, organizational awareness, system thinking, and the use of technology.

Table 3.2 presents respondents’ perceptions on the level of impact of training in the MBA program in terms of professional development and advancement.

Items	\bar{x}	DR
Involvement in policy formulation.	4.38	VGE
Involvement in program/project planning and development.	4.49	VGE
Involvement in project/program monitoring and evaluation	4.53	VGE
Involvement in human resource development.	4.50	VGE
Giving lectures and seminars.	4.47	VGE
Rendering consultancy services.	4.47	VGE
Weighted Average	4.47	VGE

The impact of their graduate school training on the professional development and advancement of the respondents was assessed through six different indicators. The MBA graduates were in the agreement that their graduate training contributed to a “very great extent” in their professional development. This was shown by the obtained mean values ranging from (4.38) to a high (4.53). All the MBA graduates felt that their graduate training produced a “very great extent” impact on their professional development and advancement as revealed by the overall weighted average mean of (4.47). Accordingly, Indolos (2008)) cited Schumacher's views that investment in the education and training of the labor force plays a crucial role in economic development.

Table 3.3 presents graduates’ perceptions of the level of impact of training in the MBA program in terms of professional recognition.

Items	\bar{x}	DR
Manifest genuine interest in development studies and /or research activities.	4.62	VGE
Participates more actively in professional organizations.	4.59	VGE
Gets invitation to share knowledge/expertise as speaker or lecturer.	4.37	VGE
Receives recognition, awards, and citations for professional practice.	4.43	VGE
Weighted Average	4.50	VGE

The impact of their graduate school training on the professional recognition of the respondents was assessed through four different indicators. The MBA graduates were in the agreement that their graduate training contributed to a “very great extent” in their professional recognition. This was shown by the obtained mean values ranging from (4.37) to a high (4.59). All the MBA graduates felt that their graduate training produced a “very great extent” impact on their professional recognition as revealed by the overall weighted average mean of (4.50). To a “very great extent” (\bar{x} = 4.50) the respondents perceived that their professional recognition training developed in them an interest in research and other development studies.

Table 3.4 presents graduates’ perceptions of the level of impact of training in the MBA program in terms of life-long skills (socio-economic development).

Items	\bar{x}	DR
Improvement in leadership skills.	4.59	VGE
Improvement in management skills.	4.63	VGE
Improvement in communications skills.	4.63	VGE
Improvement in rank.	4.57	VGE
Pay increase.	4.35	VGE
Weighted Average	4.56	VGE

As shown by the obtained values of the MBA graduates, they perceive that their graduate school training contributed to a “very great extent” in improving their management skills. Overall, the weighted average of (4.48) indicates the level of impact of training in the MBA program assessment of the graduate school to a “very great extent”. All the indicators are consistently rated to a “very great extent”.

Overall, the weighted average means of (4.48) indicates the level of impact of training in the MBA program assessment of the graduate school to a “very great extent”. All the indicators are consistently rated to a “very great extent” and are the following: training on productivity (x= 4.40), training on professional development and advancement (x=4.47), training on professional recognition (x=4.50), and life-long skills or socio-economic development (x=4.56).

4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their assessment of the performance of the MBA program?

Table 4 presents the correlation between the profile of the respondents and their assessment of the performance of the MBA program.

Correlation between Profile and Assessment of GS Program					
	Age	Sex	Civil Status	Nature of Employment	Residence
Program Relevance	.276	.256	.042	-.240	.130
Faculty Qualification	.362	.137	.062	-.053	.116
Research Facilities	.306	.111	.205	-.205	.032
Classroom & Laboratory	.169	.126	.094	-.067	-.079
Library Facilities	.197	.064	.101	.071	-.278
Achieved Goals	.259	.121	.169	-.064	-.015
± .239	The critical value of r .05 (two-tail)				
± .310	The critical value of r .01 (two-tail)				

The table shows that there is a significant relationship between age and the assessment of MBA programs in terms of program relevance (0.276 at 0.05 probability), faculty qualification (0.362 at 0.01 probability), research facilities (0.306 at 0.05 probability) and achieved goals of MBA programs (0.259 at 0.05 probability). Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents on age and their assessment of the performance of the MBA program is rejected. On the other hand, the program relevance has also a significant relationship with sex (0.256 at 0.05 probability). The hypothesis is rejected. Moreover, program relevance has a significant inverse relationship (-.240 at 0.05 probability) with the nature of employment. Hence, there is no significant relationship between program relevance and the nature of employment. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. The residence is inversely significant (-0.278) at 0.05 probability whereby there is no significant relationship between the assessment of library facilities and residences. The hypothesis is accepted.

5. Is there a significant relationship between the Profile of the respondents and the Impact of Training in the MBA Program?

Table 5

Correlation between Profile and Impact of Training Program					
	Age	Sex	Civil Status	Nature of Employment	Residence
Training on Productivity	.270	.192	.061	-.145	-.065
Training Professional Dev't	.144	.307	.007	-.054	-.181
Training on Professional Recognition	.050	.398	-.115	-.006	-.276
Training on Various Skill Dev't	.141	.229	.042	-.021	-.147
± .239	The critical value of r .05 (two-tail)				
± .310	The critical value of r .01 (two-tail)				

There is a significant relationship (0.270 at 0.05 probability) between training on productivity and age. Therefore, the hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents on age and the impact of training in the MBA program is rejected. The table further shows that Training on Professional Development (0.307 at 0.05 probability) and Training on Professional Recognition (0.398 at 0.01 probability) are significantly related to sex. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

6. Is there a significant relationship between the Assessment of the Performance of the MBA Program of the respondents and the Impact of Training in the MBA program?

Table 6

Correlation between Assessment of GS Program and Impact of Training Program						
	Program Relevance	Faculty Qualification	Research Facilities	Classroom and Laboratory Facilities	Library Facilities	Achieved Goals
Training on Productivity	.597	.542	.485	.514	.313	.593
Training on Professional Dev't.	.572	.429	.461	.458	.332	.557
Training on Professional Recognition	.510	.421	.478	.481	.417	.707
Life-long Skills (Socio-economic Dev't.)	.564	.493	.461	.556	.397	.189
± .239	The critical value of r .05 (two-tail)					
± .310	The critical value of r .01 (two-tail)					

The Impact of Training in the MBA program is significantly related to the assessment of performance in the MBA Program of DWCV except on the life-long skills or socio-economic development and achieved goals of the MBA program. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Results and Discussion

This study determined the impact of the Divine Word College of Vigan MBA Program in Region 1 and Cordillera Autonomous Region (CAR), Philippines. Results of the analysis were drawn as follows: most of the MBA graduates/graduate students at Divine Word College of Vigan are within the age range of 28 years and above, female-dominated, married, and mostly employed as professional and technical workers, more of them reside in the Cordillera Administrative Region. The MBA graduate school of Divine Word College of Vigan is performing great in terms of program relevance, faculty qualification, research facility, and achieved goals and is much appreciated by the respondents for its contribution to their development. The training given by the MBA program has a great impact on their lives as professionals as they contribute significantly to leadership and management skills. Significant relationships were found between age and sex to that assessment of performance in the MBA program; the impact on

training except for lifelong learning skills also relates to the assessment of performance in the MBA program except for the achieved goals.

Moreover, the study confirms Woodhouse's (2010) Quality Theory that a large corps of highly educated people is essential for the prosperity of society. The findings of the study suggest that the administrators review the curriculum and integrate achieving goals while strengthening lifelong learning skills training of students vis-à-vis the regular conduct of quality assurance. Subsequently, MBA programs prevail globally, as this ensures employees' job security and higher compensation.

Given these observations, the study recognized its limitations, that the respondents covered only the graduate students of DWCV. A wider study that includes all graduate schools in Region 1 will give a clear picture of the impact of the MBA program in Region 1.

Conclusion

The empirical data and analysis indicate that the respondents are mostly aged 25-29 years old, female, married, government employees, and reside in Cordillera Administrative Region. Graduates' assessment of the level of performance of the DWCV graduate program was rated while there was a great level of impact of training in the MBA program.

Further, a significant relationship was identified between age and the assessment of MBA programs in terms of program relevance, faculty qualification, research facilities, and the achieved goals of MBA programs. Program relevance significantly correlates with sex while civil status, nature of employment, and residence do not have any significant relationship with the assessment of MBA programs. The hypothesis is rejected in sex and age while it is accepted in civil status, nature of employment, and residence.

A significant relationship was also found between training on productivity and age. It further showed that training on professional development and training on professional recognition is significantly related to sex. The hypothesis is rejected. The other variables in the profile (civil status, nature of employment, and residence) are not correlated to the impact of training, hence the hypothesis is accepted.

The table further shows that the impact of training in an MBA program is significantly related to the assessment of the respondents in the MBA Program of DWCV except on the life-long skills or socio-economic development and achieved goals of the MBA program. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

These findings may be considered by the administrators for the quality evaluation of their program underscoring the facilities, inclusion of lifelong learning skills, and achieved goals of the MBA program.

Author contributions:

R. G. B: Methodology: E.B.V, R.G.B; Data Collection: E.B.V, R.G.B; Formal Analysis: E.B.V, R.G.B; Writing-Review and Editing: E.B.V, R.G.B.

Both authors have read and agreed to the published final version of the manuscript.

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